

of the alcoholic groups is bonded and the other is most probably free. In sodium potassium tartrate, two medium bands are formed at about 1110 and 1060 cm^{-1} which are probably due to C-O stretching of the two alcoholic groups. Corresponding bands in PbTOH_2 , PbT.NH_3 and $\text{PbTN}(\text{CH}_3)_3$ are respectively at 1125 and 1075 cm^{-1} , 1130 and 1094 cm^{-1} and 1125 and 1070 cm^{-1} . A little shift indicates chelation. Besides the above bands, lead(II) tartrate and its ammonia derivatives show strong and broad bands at 3480 cm^{-1} and 3270 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to $\nu\text{O}-\text{H}$ and $\nu\text{N}-\text{H}$ of water and ammonia molecule respectively. This shifting of the N-H stretching bands to lower frequency (free-ammonia 3420 cm^{-1}) is indicative of coordination through nitrogen. No definite assignments have been made for other vibrational frequencies of water or ammonia as they fall in the region of carboxylate and hydroxyl group frequencies of tartrate ligand. However, broad intensive bands in these regions may be attributed to the presence of coordinated water or ammonia (amine).

Metal-oxygen and metal-nitrogen bonds are generally found in the region below 750 cm^{-1} . In the study of copper(II) tartrate complexes⁹, the absorption bands in this region are so weak that it is difficult to characterise any distinct absorption bands in this region. In lead(II) tartrate derivatives lead atom being very heavy, the bands in this region though weak are very distinct.

The bands at 400 cm^{-1} in PbT.NH_3 and at 430 cm^{-1} in $\text{PbTN}(\text{CH}_3)_3$ are due to lead nitrogen bonds. The other bands found at 590-595 cm^{-1} , 500-510 cm^{-1} and 375-390 cm^{-1} are probably due to lead-oxygen bonds. It is therefore, very probable that Lead(II) is coordinated with two carboxylate groups and one of the two secondary alcoholic groups and a water or ammonia or amine molecule.

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References

1. M. BOBTELSKY and B. GRAUS, *Bull. Res. Coun. Israel*, 1954, **4**, 69-74.
2. V. E. PANOVA, *Zh. Neorg. Khim.*, 1956, **I**, 422.
3. R. C. PATEL, K. C. SATPATHY and S. PANI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **50**, 439-441.
4. S. KIRSCHNER and R. KIRSILING, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **82**, 4174.
5. J. D. S. GOULDEN, *Spectrochim. Acta.*, 1960, **16**, 715.

Solid Phase Interaction Between Strontium Carbonate and Urea Nitrate

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In an earlier communication a solid state interaction between dolomite and urea nitrate was reported from this laboratory¹. Strontium carbonate resembles calcium carbonate in all its properties and this prompted the author to investigate similar type of solid phase interaction between urea nitrate and strontium carbonate. The work consists of grinding strontium carbonate with urea nitrate in the mole ratio of 1 : 2 for an hour.

Experimental

1 g mole of strontium carbonate (A.R. BDH) was mixed with varying amounts of urea nitrate² and each mixture ground in an agate mortar for about an hour under dry conditions. In each case the resultant product was treated with distilled water (strontium carbonate insoluble) and filtered. In the filtrate, the amount of strontium nitrate was estimated³.

Results and Discussion

The results indicate that like dolomite-urea nitrate system¹ on grinding the mixture the protonation of strontium carbonate occurs resulting in the formation of strontium nitrate as one of the products which can be separated from insoluble strontium carbonate by dissolving the mixture in distilled water. The results reveal that with increasing urea nitrate content the percentage of water soluble strontium increases and at the stage of 1 : 2 mole ratio the solubility of the mixture becomes cent per cent. Further increase in the urea nitrate content does not give rise to increased amount of strontium nitrate in the filtrate. The limiting value of strontium nitrate found corresponds to one mole for every mole of strontium carbonate mixed with two moles of urea nitrate. Urea nitrate is an ionic salt while strontium carbonate is basic and probably on grinding the mixture an acid-base neutralization reaction occurs on account of an increase in the activation energy of the reaction

On grinding the mixture under dry conditions the textural and structural states of solid change and fresh surfaces of the reactants are exposed which enhances the rate of the chemical reaction. At the points of contact of the two solids protonation of the strontium carbonate occurs as a result of the

movement of labile H^+ ions from urea nitrate. On the basis of I.R. spectral data Davies and Hopkins⁴ concluded that the point of proton attachment is the nitrogen (structure I). On the other hand, Redpath and Smith⁵ on the basis of NMR studies favoured structure II, for urea nitrate

According to Kutty and Murthy⁶ both the structures I & II exist in the solid state because of the strong hydrogen bonding net work in the solid with comparatively high mobility for the proton. This changes the electroneutrality of strontium carbonate and causes the displacement of Sr^{2+} ions which in turn combine with the nitrate present at the inter-phase resulting in the formation of strontium nitrate. These steps occurring at the phase boundary are followed by the bulk reaction, the rate of which varies depending upon the particle size of the reactants. The movement of nitrate ions from the bulk takes place due to the concentration gradient set up by the removal of nitrate ions at the surface.

The participation of water in this reaction as adsorbed or otherwise held at the surface is ruled out by the fact that the mixture forms a paste only at the later stage of grinding. To prove that the reaction takes place simply on grinding in the solid state, physical methods like infra-red spectrum and X-ray powder diffraction are adopted, where the solvent does not play any role at all. The work is being continued in this direction.

Strontium occurs in nature as strontianite. Therefore the method described here may be utilized to concentrate strontium content from the very low grade ore.

References

1. D. N. PATHAK, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci.*, 1976, **46(A)** I, 73.
2. T. R. N. KUTTY and A. R. V. MURTHY, *Indian J. Tech.*, 1972, **10**, 305.
3. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis". 2nd Ed. Longmans Green & Co., London, 1958.
4. M. DAVIES and L. HOPKINS, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1957, **53**, 1568.
5. C. R. REDPATH and J. A. S. SMITH, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1962, **58**, 462.
6. T. R. N. KUTTY and A. R. V. MURTHY, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973 **11**, 253.

Preparation and Characterisation of Some Pyridine Compounds of Cu(II) with Molybdate, Vanadate and Tungstate Anions

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THREE new compounds $Cu(VO_3)_2 \cdot Py \cdot 3H_2O$, $CuMoO_4 \cdot 4Py \cdot 2H_2O$ and $CuWO_4 \cdot Py$ have been prepared and their I.R. spectra studied. Chemical literature of the last hundred years reveals practically no information on complexes of Cu(II) with pyridine having molybdate, vanadate and tungstate anions of the above mentioned compositions.

Experimental

Pure crystalline $CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$ (B.D.H. quality) was dissolved in minimum amount of water and to this pyridine (S. Merck) was added dropwise till the colour turned to intense blue. Thereafter, saturated solution of ammonium-metavanadate (A.R.) was added slowly with constant stirring until the precipitation was complete. The reaction mixture was digested on a water bath for nearly an hour, left overnight, filtered, washed with hot water containing a little of pyridine till free from vanadate, alcohol containing a few drops of pyridine and finally with ether. A yellowish green product obtained was dried in a vacuum desiccator and analysed.

[Found : Cu, 16% ; C, 15.52% ; H, 2.65% ; N, 3.45%, calcd. for $Cu(VO_3)_2 \cdot Py \cdot 3H_2O$: Cu, 16.10% ; C, 15.21% ; H, 2.78% ; N, 3.54%]. Exactly the same procedure was followed with ammonium molybdate (B.D.H.) and sodium tungstate (B.D.H.) solutions to get light blue and dark green substances respectively. The compounds were analysed. [Found : Cu, 10.87% ; C, 42.10% ; H, 4.05% ; N, 9.42%, calcd. for $CuMoO_4 \cdot 4Py \cdot 2H_2O$: Cu, 11.04% ; C, 41.70% ; H, 4.17% ; N, 9.73%] and [Found : Cu, 16.39% ; C, 16.20% ; H, 1.05% ; N, 3.16% ; calcd. for $CuWO_4 \cdot Py$: Cu, 16.27% ; C, 15.36% ; H, 1.28% ; N, 3.58%].

The I.R. spectra were recorded on a grating infra-red spectrometer (Perkin and Elmer Model-337) at the C.D.R.I., Lucknow.

Discussion

Pyridine vibrations have been reported¹ to be in the region of 3000 cm^{-1} because of C-H mode and other vibrations at 1578, 1550, 1478, 1436, 1372, 1350, 1217, 1145, 1085, 1067, 1031, 991, 942, 886, 747, 700, 652, 605 and 405 cm^{-1} . There is a very broad band in the region of $3600\text{ to }3000\text{ cm}^{-1}$,